

Solid State Kinetics from Thermogravimetry for Diodoquin Complexes of Barium, Magnesium and Cadmium

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Kinetic parameters, such as order of reaction, energy of activation and frequency factor are determined for the thermal decomposition of the complexes of Ba, Mg and Cd with 5, 7 Diodo-8-hydroxyquinoline (Diodoquin) (DIHQ). The methods applied are Freeman-Carroll, Coats and Redfern and Horowitz and Metzger.

For the thermal decomposition of DIHQ, complexes of Ba, Mg and Cd, the n and E values are 0, ~ 1 and 1 and 27.45, 18.06 and 18.72 Kcals/mole by Freeman-Carroll method. The E and Z values by Coats and Redfern method are 28.76, 17.56 and 18.53 Kcals/mole and 2.6×10^5 , 1.699×10^3 and $2.113 \times 10^3 \text{ sec}^{-1}$, while the values of E and Z by Horowitz and Metzger method are 29.169, 17.603 and 18.453 Kcals/mole and 2.28×10^5 , 1.58×10^3 and $2.00 \times 10^3 \text{ sec}^{-1}$ respectively.

SURVEY of literature shows that the thermal decomposition of the Ba, Mg and Cd complexes of halogenated oxines are not studied. However, mention can be made of some attempts in this field in which the complexes of these metals with somewhat related ligands were studied.

For barium attempt of Thomas¹, for magnesium attempts of Dupuis², Borrel and Paris³ and for cadmium attempts of Berg⁴ and Majumdar⁵ are some of the important contributions. But these workers too, have not determined the kinetic parameters and hence this work is undertaken in the present paper. Kinetic parameters like the order of reaction, n , the activation energy, E and the frequency factor, Z are determined by the application of Freeman-Carroll method⁶, Coats and Redfern method⁷ and Horowitz-Metzger method⁸.

Experimental

Thermogravimetry :

Thermograms were taken with a Stanton self recording thermobalance of 1 mg sensitivity using 100 m gms of the sample in a platinum crucible. The heating rate was maintained to be constant at 6° per minute.

The details of preparation of the complex and the metal estimation in each is given in our earlier publication⁹. The complexes were prepared in 1:2 (M:L) ratio and it was confirmed by estimation of elements.

In Freeman-Carroll method the values of dW/dT are obtained from the temperature vs weight loss curves, while in Horowitz-Metzger method T_s is taken as the reference temperature at which dW/dT is maximum.

Results and Discussion

Figure 1 represents a plot in weight loss vs temperature as read from the therm grams. The curve A is for Ba-DIHQ complex, curve B for Mg-DIHQ complex and curve C for Cd-DIHQ complex. The

Fig. 1. Curve A—For Ba-DIHQ Complex.
Curve B—For Mg-DIHQ Complex
Curve C—For Cd-DIHQ Complex

I—First step
II—Second step
X-axis—Temp. °C
Y-axis—Weight loss in mgms.

decompositions of DIHQ complexes of Ba, Mg and Cd starts at 230°, 200° and 210° respectively. All these curves are quite steep in the beginning representing faster reactions and thus if the process as a whole is considered as one step, reliable results are not obtained. Thus the whole process of decomposition, in case of each complex, is regarded to be taking place in two steps as shown in the figure. I steps upto 350°, 350° and 330° and II steps above these temperatures for the respective complexes. Since in all these cases the II steps are complete, therefore they are taken into account for obtaining the results. The difference in final weight loss of the II steps and the weight loss at the beginning of the step is regarded as the final weight loss and the weight losses at the starting temperatures of these steps are treated as zero. Accordingly the results are recorded in the Table 1 (for Ba-DIHQ), Table 2 (for Mg-DIHQ) and Table 3 (for Cd-DIHQ) for all the three methods.

The curves A, B and C do not show any horizontal portions indicating that no stable intermediate compound is formed. But weight loss ceases near about 560° in case of Ba-DIHQ complex and this might be due to the formation of BaCO₃ in accordance with Thomas¹⁰. Similarly the formation of oxides of Mg and Cd above 570° and above 600° respectively, are indicated which is also in agreement with Thomas¹¹ for magnesium.

If the weight loss at any particular temperature (380°C) is observed in these cases, then it appears that they follow the order Mg > Cd > Ba, indicating that they should have the order of their stability as Ba > Cd > Mg. This order is in accordance with the natural order of stability given by Irving-Williams¹². This order is also supported by the entropy values¹³ of Ba, Cd and Mg. The same conclusion can be drawn at some higher temperature (440°C).

TABLE 1—BARIUM COMPLEX OF DIODOQUIN (DIHQ)

S. No.	Temp. °K	Freeman-Carroll method		$\frac{\Delta \log \frac{dW}{dT}}{\Delta \log W_r}$	α	Coats-Redfern method		Horowitz-Metzger method	
		W_r	$\frac{\Delta \frac{1}{T} \times 10^3}{\Delta \log W_r}$			$\frac{1}{T} \times 10^3$	$\left[\frac{-\log \frac{-\ln(1-\alpha)}{T^2}}{\theta} \right]$	T_s is 803°K	$\ln \ln \frac{W_0}{W}$
1	653	51.0	—	—	0.0097	1.5313	7.6341	-150	-4.6159
2	663	50.5	5.3721	-40.93	0.01942	1.508	7.3516	-140	-3.9462
3	673	50.0	5.2093	-29.07	0.0291	1.4858	7.1865	-130	-3.5250
4	683	49.0	2.4660	-11.00	0.0485	1.4641	6.9721	-120	-3.0013
5	693	47.5	1.5630	-10.83	0.0777	1.4430	6.7727	-110	-2.5887
6	703	46.5	2.2391	0.0	0.0971	1.4224	6.6842	-100	-2.2878
7	713	45.0	1.3916	-7.63	0.1262	1.4025	6.5762	-90	-2.005
8	723	42.5	0.7823	-3.52	0.1748	1.3831	6.4355	-80	-1.6489
9	733	39.5	0.5943	-2.28	0.2330	1.3642	6.3065	-70	-1.3272
10	743	37.0	0.6479	-3.18	0.2816	1.3458	6.2222	-60	-1.1061
11	753	33.0	0.3582	-1.5	0.3592	1.328	6.1050	-50	-0.8088
12	763	28.5	0.2732	-1.0	0.4466	1.3106	5.9927	-40	-0.5258
13	773	24.0	0.2279	-0.744	0.5340	1.2936	5.8935	-30	-0.2697
14	783	19.5	0.1829	-0.37	0.6214	1.2771	5.8002	-20	-0.029
15	793	15.0	0.1413	-0.139	0.7087	1.261	5.7074	-10	+0.2102
16	803	12.0	0.1651	-0.157	0.7670	1.245	5.646	+0	+0.376
17	813	8.0	0.0852	+0.2686	0.8447	1.23	5.5499	+10	+0.6216
18	823	5.5	0.0922	0.0	0.8932	1.215	5.481	+20	+0.8054
19	833	3.0	0.0555	+0.433	0.9417	1.20	5.3875	+30	+1.0453

TABLE 2—MAGNESIUM COMPLEX OF DIODOQUIN (DIHQ)

S. No.	Temp. °K	Wr	Freeman Carroll method		α	Coats-Redfern method $\frac{1}{T} \times 10^3$	$\left[\frac{-\log(1-\alpha)}{T^2} \right]_{\theta}$	Horowitz-Metzger method T _s is 773°K	
			$\frac{\Delta \frac{1}{T} \times 10^3}{\Delta \log Wr}$	$\frac{\Delta \log \frac{dW}{dT}}{\Delta \log Wr}$				ln	$\ln \frac{W_0}{W}$
1	653	49.0	—	—	0.0666	1.5313	6.7918	-120	-2.6795
2	673	46.0	1.6606	-19.854	0.1238	1.4858	6.5349	-100	-2.0262
3	693	42.5	1.2442	-4.5058	0.1905	1.443	6.3563	-80	-1.5568
4	713	37.0	0.6727	-1.8903	0.2952	1.4025	6.1620	-60	-1.0506
5	733	30.5	0.4565	-1.0763	0.419	1.3642	5.9952	-40	-0.6112
6	753	23.5	0.3198	-0.4514	0.5524	1.328	5.8484	-20	-0.2183
7	773	17.0	0.2449	-0.167	0.6762	1.2936	5.7244	0	+0.1197
8	793	12.5	0.2442	0.0	0.7619	1.261	5.6418	+20	+0.3611
9	813	8.5	0.1851	+0.1403	0.8381	1.23	5.5599	+40	+0.5995
10	833	5.0	0.1285	+0.4735	0.9048	1.2004	5.4698	+60	+0.8556
11	853	22.0	0.0706	+0.4824	0.9619	1.1723	5.3476	+80	+1.1844

TABLE 3—CADMIUM COMPLEX OF DIODOQUIN (DIHQ)

S. No.	Temp. °K	Wr	Freeman-Carroll method		α	Coats-Redfern method $\frac{1}{T} \times 10^3$	$\left[\frac{-\log(1-\alpha)}{T^2} \right]_{\theta}$	Horowitz-Metzger method T _s is 773°K	
			$\frac{\Delta \frac{1}{T} \times 10^3}{\Delta \log Wr}$	$\frac{\Delta \log \frac{dW}{dT}}{\Delta \log Wr}$				ln	$\ln \frac{W_0}{W}$
1	633	52.0	—	—	0.0095	1.5797	7.6174	-140	-4.6880
2	653	50.0	2.8412	-5.700	0.0476	1.5314	6.9412	-120	-3.0202
3	673	49.5	10.364	-18.159	0.0571	1.4858	6.8872	-100	-2.8354
4	693	46.5	1.5793	-5.533	0.1143	1.4430	6.5966	-80	-2.1116
5	713	42.5	1.0358	-3.358	0.1905	1.4025	6.3811	-60	-1.5561
6	733	37.5	0.7040	-1.5777	0.2857	1.3642	6.2033	-40	-1.0895
7	753	32.0	0.5254	-1.0348	0.3905	1.3280	6.0589	-20	-0.7031
8	773	25.0	0.3209	-0.1213	0.5238	1.2936	5.9061	0	-0.2985
9	793	19.5	0.8021	0.0	0.6286	1.261	5.8028	+20	-0.0097
10	813	14.0	0.2154	+0.1828	0.7333	1.23	5.699	+40	+0.2791
11	833	10.0	0.2026	+0.1923	0.8095	1.2004	5.6217	+60	+0.5057
12	853	6.0	0.1267	+0.4369	0.8857	1.1773	5.5256	+80	+0.7745
13	873	2.0	0.564	+0.6347	0.9619	1.1454	5.3678	+100	+1.1844

Kinetics from Thermograms :

The weight losses are read from the weight loss temperature curves at a temperature interval of 10° in case of Ba-DIHQ and at an interval of 20° in cases of Mg-DIHQ and Cd-DIHQ.

Fairly good straight line plots are obtained for all the three methods applied to all the metals.

In the applicability of Freeman-Carroll method some abnormal points are avoided to get a clear picture about most of the points. Similarly in Coats and Redfern method and Horowitz-Metzger method, the straight line plots have either some points in the beginning or some at the end which did not fall on the straight line. This is expected since the decomposition of solids is known not to obey, first order kinetics perfectly, which is as per the observation of Jacobs and Tompkins¹⁴ and Coats and Redfern¹⁵.

The decomposition of the DIHQ complexes of Ba, Mg and Cd have the subsequent values of the order of reaction as zero, nearly one and one. The values of E obtained for Ba-DIHQ complex are 27.456, 28.763 and 29.169 Kcals/mole by the three methods respectively, while for Mg-DIHQ the values are 18.06, 17.563 and 17.603 Kcals/mole and for Cd-DIHQ the values are 18.72, 18.537 and 18.453 Kcals/mole. It clearly shows that the values of E obtained by the three methods for each complex are in perfect agreement. Similarly the values of Z calculated by the latter two methods for Ba-DIHQ are 2.6×10^5 and 2.285×10^5 sec⁻¹, for Mg-DIHQ the values are 1.699×10^2 and 1.586×10^2 sec⁻¹, while for Cd-DIHQ the values are 2.113×10^2 and 2.005×10^2 sec⁻¹. These values of Z by both the methods and for each complex perfectly agree with each other.

Thus the order of E values of Ba, Mg and Cd is Ba > Cd > Mg, which is exactly the same as said before and is also interpretable on the basis of their entropy values, but on the basis of electropositive character the order predicted is Ba > Mg > Cd, which is not perfectly in agreement.

Looking to the abnormally low values of Z, it is concluded that the reactions of decompositions of DIHQ complexes of Ba, Mg and Cd can be classed as "Slow" reactions and any other probable reason cannot be given.

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